

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Using Artificial Intelligence for secondary analysis of ZEB34A clinical trials data

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

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I. Data areas and data types

A retrospective quantitative secondary analysis of clinical trial data comprising histology images, genomic sequence data (whole exome sequence and 500 gene panel data), electronic case report form (CRF) data and electronic healthcare records.

II. Standards and metadata

Standard metadata, produced as per the ZEB34A clinical trial, will be utilised for this secondary analysis study. Details of the methodologies used to characterise and analyse the primary data will be recorded. All outputs from this project will be accompanied by appropriate documentation, code commenting and update to resources designed for this purpose. This project will follow the UK Data Service guidelines for describing qualitative data.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

Data in this project comes from a single source – the ZEB34A clinical trial, managed by the University. Data for this trial has been uploaded into the ISRCTN registry. All study records for this primary dataset are freely accessible and searchable. Data curated in the ZEB34A sub-study are not publicly available yet, due to ongoing research.

IV. Secondary use

Due to this project being a secondary analysis of clinical trial data, data controllership and consent model, this project is limited for further analysis, and the subsequent utility of this data may also be limited. The primary datasets are under the Data Controllership of the University Clinical Trials Unit, whereby the University is the designated Sponsor and data controller. Access to these primary datasets may be accessed through negotiation and contact with the University Clinical Trials Unit.

V. Methods for data sharing

Following publication, we intend to publish the data from this sub-study to the ISRCTN Registry to ensure reusability and accessibility of these findings, citing the main ZEB34A clinical trial, which is also listed within this publicly accessible registry. ISRCTN registry attributes a unique object identification (UOI) number, which may be referenced in future citations.

VI. Proprietary data

Participants of the ZEB34A clinical trial provided consent for anonymised data to be shared with approved projects for future research. Due to this sub-study project being a secondary analysis of clinical trial data, data controllership and consent model, this project is limited for additional analysis, and the subsequent utility of this data may also be limited.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be shared in a timely manner and shared publicly at the time of its publication, or within one year from the project end date.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

Data in this project comes from a single source – the ZEB34A clinical trial, managed by the University. The final pseudonymised prepared for long-term storing, with consideration to conversion and future use. Data will be stored in csv format as an open, standard, interchangeable and longer-lasting format, thus maximising the potential for future utility. For long-term digital preservation, the University RDSS archives data in open and standard formats.